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RESEARCHER MENTAL HEALTH OVERVIEW IN (ALBANIA)

Written by

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Country Profile [1]

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Location

Southeastern Europe, bordering the Adriatic Sea and Ionian Sea, between Greece to the south and Montenegro and Kosovo to the north

Capital: Tirana

Area: 28,748 sq km

Major language: Albanian

Population: 2.7 million

Life expectancy: 74 years (men) 80 years (women)

Border Countries

Greece 212 km; Kosovo 112 km;
North Macedonia 181 km;
Montenegro 186 km

Religion

Muslim 56.7%, Roman Catholic 10%,
Orthodox 6.8%, atheist 2.5%,
Bektashi (a Sufi order) 2.1%, other
5.7%, unspecified 16.2% (2011 est.)

Ethnic groups

Albanian 82.6%, Greek 0.9%, other
1% (including Vlach, Romani,
Macedonian, Montenegrin, and
Egyptian), unspecified 15.5% (2011
est.)

Administrative divisions

12 counties (qarqe, singular - qark); Berat, Diber,
Durrës, Elbasan, Fier, Gjirokaster, Korçë, Kukës, Lezhë,
Shkodër, Tiranë (Tirana), Vlorë

1.

Albania - The World Factbook
(cia.gov)

WHAT'S IN THE NEWS

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Albania ranks among the countries with the highest levels of mental health issues, holding the 18th position out of 38 transition countries in the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) Transition Report for the year 2023

Females suffer more than males from mental health issues in all countries, including Albania. [2]

Mental health treatment in Albania is regulated by Law no. 44 of 2012 (adopted 19 April 2012), and a series of bylaws passed in 2013 and 2014 to facilitate the implementation of its provisions. [2] In parallel with the drafting and adoption of Law 44/2012, an 'Action Plan for the Development of Mental Health Services 2013-2022' was developed

Albania is party to the European Convention on Human Rights [ECHR] [3] and the European Social Charter (November 2002)[4], and has also ratified the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities [5] and the UN Convention against Torture and other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (May 1994)[6]

1. Law no. 44/2012: 19 April 2012 (unofficial translation)
2. European Union, EU Fundamental Rights Information System, accessed 23 November 2022
3. Council of Europe, 'Albania and the European Social Charter', March 2022
4. UN Treaty Body database. Last accessed 23 November 2022
5. UN CRPD, State party report (paragraph 46) dated 3 October 2017

Mental Health Workforce in Albania

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According to the World Health Organisation's Mental Health Atlas 2020, published 8 October 2021, health professionals in Albania numbered as follows:[10]

	Total number (gov. and non gov.)	No. per 100,000 population
Psychiatrists	46	1.6
Mental health nurses	250	8.68
Psychologists	43	1.49
Social workers	34	1.18
Other specialised mental health workers (e.g. occupational therapists)	20	0.69
Total mental health professionals	393	13.64

The WHO Mental Health Atlas 2020 showed that upper-middle-income economy countries had, on average (median), 1.7 psychiatrists and 14.7 total mental health workers per 100,000 population

In apparent contrast with the data from WHO, the Order of Psychologists in the Republic of Albania, a professional body established by statute, stated in their 2017 Annual Report that their membership included 307 licenced psychologists, of whom 147 were clinical psychologists. (However, it was not made clear whether all of the members of the Order were actually based in Albania.) [11]

10. WHO Mental Health Atlas 2020: Albania country profile, 8 October 2021

11. Order of Psychologists in the Republic of Albania, 'Annual Report 2017', January 2018.

Overview of academic context in Albania

Funding for research and academia

The Albanian national research system is regulated by the Albanian Law “No.80/2015 on Higher Education and Scientific Research in the Higher Education Institutions” [12]

According to article 110 of the Law on Higher Education and Decision of Council of Ministers no. 75, dated 12.02.2018 "On the approval of the financing model", as amended, the State Budget is distributed to Higher Education Institutions in the form of a grant consisting of:

- **-The teaching grant** is administered by the **National Agency for Financing Higher Education (NAFHE)**, and should not be less than 85% of the total annual grant.
- **-The Development policy grant** for public institutions of higher education is administered by the **Ministry of Education and Sports** and should be up to 10% of the total annual grant. The State funded (public) higher education institutions (HEIs) enjoy financial autonomy guaranteed by the law on higher education
- **The grant for scientific research** work and creative activities is administered by the **National Agency for Scientific Research and Innovation (NASRI)**[12] which distributes this grant based on the criteria approved by DCM no. 75/2019. This grant should be 5% to 10% of the total annual grant. Differently from the two other grants, the scientific research and creative activities grant might finance both public and private HIEs and scientific research institutions, which in this case compete for these grants equally

The National Agency for Scientific Research and Innovation (NASRI) [12]

is a public legal institution under the competencies of the Ministry of Education and Sports which is responsible for the funding of research in Albania. NASRI aims to build a modern system of science and strengthen research and technology in alignment with national priorities, collaborating with all relevant institutions and sectors. As the national coordinator for Horizon Europe and Euroaxess, NASRI is responsible for promoting Albania in European initiatives. NASRI funds 4 types of research projects

1. Research and development
2. Infrastructure projects
3. Bilateral projects, in collaboration with other countries
4. Industria-academia projects

The National Agency for Higher Education Financing (NAHEF)

is a public institution under the authority of the Ministry of Education and Sports responsible for allocating public funds to support the activities of public higher education institutions and provide scholarship support for excellent students who achieved high grades in the secondary and tertiary higher education system.

[12] Agjencia Kombëtare e Kërkimit Shkencor dhe Inovacionit.
<https://nasri.gov.al/>

National funds for research in Albania.

NASRI launched the first call for financing **research infrastructure projects** in 2019. In the framework of this initiative, it has financed 15 *National Research Infrastructure Projects* with a total of 164,000,000 ALL or 1.4 million Euro grant from the public budget. Funding for scientific research has been extremely low, accounting for less than 0.1% of GDP [13].

In 2023, NASRI opened the first call for **joint academia-business projects** in the field of innovation where 10 joint projects were founded (total amount EUR 170,000). Albania **increased funding** for scientific research to 0.08% of GDP in 2023, up from 0.05% in 2022 and 0.04% in 2021, however, this is still far below the target 1% of GDP by 2030. A new Law on the creation, organisation and operation of **technology and science parks** was also adopted in July 2022 [14]. Since 2022, the start-up fund has been managed by the Minister of State for the Protection of Entrepreneurship. The fund granted EUR 2.5 million to 58 beneficiaries in 2022.

[13] Republic of Albania, Councils of Ministers (2024). Economic Reform Programme 2024-2026. 2024.

<https://www.investment.com.al/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/Economic-Reform-Programme-2024-2026.pdf>

[14] LAW No. 58/2022 ON THE CREATION, ORGANIZATION AND OPERATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL AND SCIENTIFIC PARKS

<https://aicorporation.al/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/Ligj-Nr.-58-2022-Per-Krijimin-Organizimin-Dhe-Funksionimin-E-Parqev-Teknologjike-Dhe-Shkencore.pdf>

Active Participation of Albania in European Projects

Albania has participated in the EU Research and Innovation programs since 2008. Since then, it has been actively involved in setting up an R&I governance system to align with the ERA priorities. Albania's annual activities in Horizon 2020 have been growing rapidly since 2014 and it has been particularly successful in the area of Health research. The Association Agreement with Albania, ensuring its participation in Horizon Europe, was entered into force on 30 May 2022. [15].

The sharply increased participation in COST actions is another successful outcome of these efforts. Currently, there are 292 running COST actions with Albania participating in 74% of them. The country's efforts for integration in the ERA and implementation of the ERA Policy Agenda are laid out in the National Economic Reform Program 2024- 2026[3]. Moreover, the ongoing development of a Smart Specialization Strategy will further strengthen Albania's national research and innovation eco-system [16].

In 2022, Albania participated for the first time in the European analysis of the European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS), with data being collected for 23 indicators (out of 32 in the full framework) [17]. Albania is an Emerging Innovator with a performance of 41.1% of the EU average.

Albanian institutions participated in 10 international projects related to the development of national research infrastructures in the period from 2008 to 2020 [18]. The total budget of Albanian institutions for the implementation of these projects is about 390.000 EUR (EC contribution).

Albania *	Performance relative to EU in 2023	Performance change 2016-2023	Performance change 2022-2023
SUMMARY INNOVATION INDEX	41.1	6.6	-1.7
Human resources	53.6	17.8	0.0
Doctorate graduates	10.0	-0.5	0.0
Population with tertiary education	75.3	56.3	0.0
Lifelong learning	79.4	0.0	0.0
Attractive research systems	42.0	17.7	3.3
International scientific co-publications	6.1	8.7	0.0
Most cited publications	55.4	52.9	6.3
Foreign doctorate students	58.6	-54.8	-0.8
Digitalisation	4.1	0.0	0.0
Broadband penetration	7.1	0.0	0.0
People with above basic overall digital skills	0.0	0.0	0.0
Finance and support	0.0	0.0	0.0
R&D expenditures in the public sector**	0.0	0.0	0.0
Venture capital expenditures	N/A	N/A	N/A
Government support for business R&D	N/A	N/A	N/A
Firm investments	0.0	0.0	0.0
R&D expenditure in the business sector**	0.0	0.0	0.0
Non-R&D Innovation expenditures	N/A	N/A	N/A
Innovation expenditures per employee	N/A	N/A	N/A

Source: European Innovation Scoreboard 2023 Country profile Albania

The second column shows performance relative to that of the EU in 2023. Colors next to the column show matching color codes: dark green: above 125% of the performance of the EU in 2023; light green: between 100% and 125%; light orange: between 70% and 100%; dark orange: below 70%. The next columns show performance change over time between 2016 and 2023 and between 2022 and 2023, with scores relative to those of the EU in 2016. Positive (negative) performance changes are shown in green (red).

[15] COMMISSION STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT. Albania 2023 Report. Brussels, 8.11.2023 SWD(2023) 690 final. https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-11/SWD_2023_690%20Albania%20report.pdf

[16] Strategjia e Specializimit Inteligent S3. <https://s3albania.org/>

[17] European Innovation Scoreboard 2023 – Country profile Albania. June 2023.

https://ec.europa.eu/assets/rtd/eis/2023/ec_rtd_eis-country-profile-al.pdf

[18] Research Infrastructure Roadmap for Albania. Regional Cooperation Council . Djuro Kutlaca and Lazar Zivkovic. March 2022. [file:///C:/Users/i.mehmeti/Downloads/Ri%20Roadmap%20Albania%20digital%20\(2\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/i.mehmeti/Downloads/Ri%20Roadmap%20Albania%20digital%20(2).pdf)

Figure 3: Participation in Horizon Europe programmes by thematic priority

Source: Albanian’s ERA integration: An update by Policy Answers.

The net EU contribution by thematic priority is: 1.44 million euros under WIDERA, 0.18 million euros under Excellent Science, and 0.13 million euros under Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness, making a total of 1.75 million euros during 2021 and 2022 under Horizon Europe

Practices and Policies in Higher Education

Law No. 247/2010

"On Albanian Qualification Framework" has the objective of determining the levels of the Albanian Qualification Framework (AQF), and the types of qualifications, qualifying for these levels so that the process is based on standards of knowledge, skills, and competencies [20].

Capacity building

Across various Albanian universities, capacity building and project proposal writing skills are paramount. However, the level of existing skills and the emphasis on capacity building vary significantly, leading to differences in research output and success in securing project funding. The Albanian government has included improving human capacities for Research and Innovation under its Economic Reform Programme (ERP), reform measure no. 03 "Improving institutional, financial and human capacities for research and innovation" [13].

The Syndicate of University Workers in Albania (SPUSH)

is a voluntary union of teachers, pedagogues, scientists and other employees who are employed in the system of the Ministry of Education and Science and the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Albania, regardless of political and party affiliations, of ideological beliefs and religious beliefs. It aims to represent and protect the economic and social interests of education and science workers [19].

Young researchers

The Albanian government has included "Increasing innovation and skills for young people and adults to enhance employment" as key challenge no. 1 of the Economic Recovery Plan 2024-2026 [13]. The 2022-2029 national strategy for youth adopted in October 2022 integrates the empowerment through self-defense approach as part of the extra-curricular programs of public schools [21]. The selection of Tirana as European Youth of Capital 2022 enhanced the local and national ecosystem for the development of youth policies

[19] The Syndicate of University Workers in Albania (SPUSH) (2023). <https://spushal.com/>

[20] Law No. 247/2010 "On Albanian Qualification Framework" https://qsha.gov.al/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/ligj_10247-2010_04032010.pdf

[21] National Youth Strategy and Action Plan 2022-2029 Ministry of Health for Youth and Children. 2022.

https://riniafemijet.gov.al/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/SKR29_Anglisht.pdf

Internationalization of research

The new Law on Science including Open Science, Knowledge Valorization, and Research Infrastructure and Facilities will support a stronger R&I ecosystem aligned with the ERA Policy Agenda priorities. Albania has launched its EURAXESS Profile with very little information on Albania's attractiveness in R&I [23]

Mental Health in Accademia

Recent developments within the academic system, including issues concerning mental health, the trajectory of researchers' careers, funding allocation, research culture, and matters of equity, diversity, and inclusion (EDI), have become focal points of discussion. In the context of Albania, these concerns can be likened to an unexplored territory, where the primary challenge lies in securing the fundamental rights and resources necessary for academic work. Mental health issues, often regarded as somewhat exotic, have surfaced as pertinent challenges faced by researchers and academic staff in the Albanian context.

Erasmus+

Albania continued to participate in Erasmus+ and the European Solidarity Corps. In 2022, approximately 900 higher education staff members and 1 280 students from Albania were selected to undertake a mobility period in EU Member States or associated third countries to the program. The number of higher education capacity-building projects selected for funding increased from 12 in 2020 to 17 in 2022. Albania is participating in the European Education Area working groups 2021- 2025 [22]

[22] <https://education.ec.europa.eu/about-eea/working-groups>

[23] <https://www.euraxess.al/>

Career Guidance

All 43 universities (16 public and 27 non-public) have appointed full-time staff to manage the Career and Alumni Centers. They have made available an office within the institutions and are offering Career Guidance which is very important for student orientation and facilitating connections between the academic career and employment opportunities

Inclusive education

On inclusive education, the number of children with disabilities in public and private educational institutions (starting from preschool education) has increased to 4 748 students. In 2022-2023, the number of assistant teachers for students with disabilities in the public preuniversity education system went up by about 17% compared with the previous year (1 300 assistant teachers in total)

Gender balance

Gender gaps still exist in education as, according to INSTAT, the enrolment rate in compulsory education is 98.7% for boys and 92.7% for girls [24]. Participation in upper secondary education is higher for boys than girls, at 98.7% and 89.9% respectively. Whereas for higher education the participation rate is higher for girls (73.2%) than for boys (49.6%). In vocational education, approximately 82% of graduates are males.

[24] INSTAT Albania. (2023). Education. <https://www.instat.gov.al/al/temat/tregu-i-pun%C3%ABs-dhe-arsimi/arsimi/>.

Academic system in the country

Higher Education Governing Bodies

Based on the law on higher education, the following authorities are responsible for higher education policies in Albania

Ministry of Education and Sport (MES) [Ministria e Arsimit dhe Sportit] [25]

is responsible for drafting policies in the area of higher education and scientific research and for approving respective strategic plans in this regards

The Council of Higher Education and Scientific Research [Këshilli i Arsimit të Lartë dhe Kërkimit Shkencor]

is an advisory body for the policies of higher education and scientific research, subordinated to the minister responsible for education

Conference of Rectors [Konferenca e Rektorëve]

The Conference of Rectors is a collegial, independent body, composed of the heads of higher education institutions and it is responsible for carrying out activities of coordination and development of higher education and scientific research and gives recommendations related to higher education issues of national interest

Education Service Center [Qendra për Shërbime Arsimore][27]

CES has as its responsibility the provision of services in the field of higher education and the provision of public access to data on higher education.

Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education [Agjencia për Sigurimin e Cilësisë në Arsimin e Lartë][26]

The Agency is responsible for quality assurance in higher education, monitors and evaluates the quality of the institution and the programs offered. AQHE supports its activity in the Higher Education Quality Code, which is updated with European Quality Standards and Guidelines (ESG)

Accreditation Board

The Accreditation Board is established at the Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education. The Board is a collegial decision-making body and independent in its activity of evaluating and deciding on the accreditation of higher education institutions and the study programs they offer

National Agency for Higher Education Financing (NAHEF) [Agjencia Kombëtare për Financimin e Arsimit të Lartë]

The main responsibility of this institution is distributing public funds for supporting the activity of public institutions of higher education, for teaching, scientific research and participation in academic and administrative management issues

Albanian Academic Network [Rrjeti Akademik Shqiptar] (RASH)[28]

This institution is a structure established after the higher education reform of 2015 and its activity directly affects the implementation of policies related to scientific research and cooperation between higher education institutions. RASH aims to develop and promote research development and innovation projects in the field of information and communication technology (ICT) for education and science

National Agency for Scientific Research and Innovation [Agjencia Kombëtare për Kërkim Shkencor dhe Inovacion]

[25] <https://arsimi.gov.al/>

[26] Agjencia e Sigurimit të Cilësisë në Arsimin e Lartë. <https://ascal.al/sq/>

[27] Qendra e Shërbimeve Arsimore. QSHA – Qendra e Shërbimeve Arsimore

[28] Albanian Academic Network. <https://www.rash.al/sq/>

Currently, there are 43 higher education institutions (HEIs) in Albania, of which 16 are public and 27 nonpublic. Also, there are about 20 institutes, centers, and other institutions that perform research activities beyond the competence of line ministries. The types of higher education institutions are universities, university colleges, academies, and professional higher education colleges. Higher education institutions are organized into public, non-public, and independent public institutions. Higher education institutions are created, opened, organized, financed, accredited, evaluated, suspended, and closed in accordance with the law on Higher Education in Albania

Public higher education institutions are public legal entities that self-finance and are financed by the State Budget, or other legal sources

Non-public higher education institutions are private legal entities. Their activities may be for-profit or non-profit

Independent public higher education institutions are public legal entities created by the decision of the Council of Ministers, according to the provisions of this law

Higher education institutions consist of core units, basic units, and other units, according to the provisions in the statute of the higher education institution. Higher education institutions that offer study programs in specific academic fields related to the organization and development of the educational process enjoy special status. This status is granted to the higher education institution by the decision of the Council of Ministers, based on the proposal of the ministry responsible for higher education [29].

Core units are faculties, research, and scientific institutes, and professional higher education colleges, in cases when they are established within higher education institutions that have the status of universities and university colleges

Basic units are departments and research and scientific centers

[29] Council of Ministers Decision no. 109, dated 15.02.2017 on The organization and functioning of the Quality Assurance Agency in Higher Education and the accreditation board and determination of the fees for the quality assurance processes in higher education
<https://www.ascal.al/media/documents/legjislacioni/No.%20109,%20dated%2015.02.2017.pdf>

Study Formats and Admission to Higher Education Institutions

Study Formats

The study formats in higher education institutions are

- a) Full-time studies;
- b) Extended-time studies. Extended-time studies may be offered in one to two-year professional study programs, second-cycle programs "Professional Master," and third-cycle programs "Executive Master."

Study programs that provide the right to practice a regulated profession are only organized in the form of full-time studies

Admission of Students

Admission of students to higher education institutions in all study programs is made by the decisions of the institutions, in accordance with state standards, and academic and infrastructural capacities. These standards are verified and certified by the ministry responsible for education, before the declaration of admission quotas by all higher education institutions

Study Cycles and Programs

Higher education institutions offer study programs organized in modules and evaluated in credits, in accordance with the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS). The normal amount of credits accumulated during an academic year by a student is 60 ECTS credits.

Study programs are developed by the base units of higher education institutions and approved by their academic senates and they are organized in three consecutive cycles: the first cycle, the second cycle, and the third cycle, referring to levels 6-8 of the Albanian Qualifications Framework. Higher education institutions also offer professional diplomas, referring to level 5 of the Albanian Qualifications Framework. Higher education institutions publicly announce open and accredited study programs before the start of student admissions

Scientific research in Academia

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH ACTIVITIES ARE CONDUCTED, ACCORDING TO THE PROVISIONS OF THIS LAW, IN:

A) HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH ACTIVITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS ARE CARRIED OUT BASED ON APPROVED PROGRAMS AND PROJECTS BY COMPETENT BODIES WITHIN THESE INSTITUTIONS, IN ACCORDANCE WITH THE INSTITUTION'S STATUTES AND REGULATIONS. AREAS, DIRECTIONS, WORKLOAD, AND DEADLINES FOR RESEARCH ACTIVITIES ARE DETERMINED BY HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS BASED ON PRIORITY AREAS OF NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT AND THE PROGRAMS OFFERED. HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS HAVE THE RIGHT TO DEVELOP RESEARCH PROGRAMS AND PROJECTS IN COLLABORATION WITH OTHER PUBLIC OR PRIVATE INSTITUTIONS, BOTH WITHIN AND OUTSIDE THE COUNTRY. HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS, THROUGH RESEARCH AND CREATIVE ACTIVITIES, OFFER SERVICES FOR THIRD PARTIES

B) INTERINSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTES

AND CENTERS ARE CREATED BY TWO OR MORE HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS OR BY A HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION WITH RESEARCH AND SCIENTIFIC, CULTURAL, AND ECONOMIC INSTITUTIONS, BOTH PUBLIC AND PRIVATE, THROUGH AGREEMENTS BETWEEN THEM.

C) RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTES WITHIN MINISTRIES

RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTES AND CENTERS WITHIN THE INSTITUTIONS OF HIGHER EDUCATION CONDUCT RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENTAL ACTIVITIES AND SERVE TO COMPLETE THE SECOND AND THIRD-CYCLE EDUCATION PROGRAMS.

The main ministries and institutions responsible for scientific research in Albania are:

1. Ministry of Education and Sports;
2. Council for Higher Education for Scientific Research;
3. National Agency for Scientific Research and Innovation;
4. Higher Education Institutions
5. Institute of Statistics - INSTAT;
6. Ministry of Finance and Economy;
7. Ministry of Health and Social Protection;
8. Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development;
9. Ministry of Infrastructure and Energy;
10. Ministry of Tourism and Environment
11. RASH - National Network of Academics

Career track for researcher in the country

Categories of Academic Staff

Academic staff in higher education institutions performs teaching, scientific research, services for the support and development of the higher education institution, counseling for students, and other activities.

Academic staff may be focused on teaching and/or research-scientific orientation. Academic staff in higher education institutions, based on their roles and activities, is categorized as

Professors

includes members of academic staff, titular in subjects or modules, and leaders of research-scientific activities. Members of academic staff in this category hold the academic titles "Professor" or "Associate Professor." This category is employed on contracts with unspecified durations

Lecturers

members of academic staff who conduct teaching and research-scientific activities are included. This category includes members of academic staff holding the academic degree of "Doctor," having at least three years of teaching experience before or after obtaining this degree, and meeting the criteria specified in the statute of the higher education institution. This category is employed on contracts with unspecified durations

Assistant Lecturers

members of academic staff conducting teaching-research activities are included. Assistant Lecturers must have at least a "Master of Science" degree and meet the criteria specified in the statute of the higher education institution. Assistant Lecturers are employed on contracts with specified durations

Acquisition of Academic Titles

To acquire the title "Associate Professor," academic staff holding the academic degree "Doctor" for at least five years, being academic staff of the "Lecturer" category, and meeting state standards for obtaining the title, may apply. To acquire the title "Professor," academic staff holding the title "Associate Professor" for at least five years and meeting state standards for obtaining the title may apply.

The candidate for the title "Associate Professor" or "Professor" submits the dossier to the head of the main unit. The candidate's dossier is forwarded to the academic senate, after presentation and evaluation in the base unit. The senate passes the dossier to the Permanent Commission for the Promotion of Academic Staff, which makes the final decision after the committee's decision on meeting the standards. The title is registered in the state register of scientific degrees and academic titles at the ministry responsible for education. The academic title is issued by the institution and signed by the rector.

Allocation of the academic titles

The academic titles "Professor" and "Associate Professor" are awarded by higher education institutions of the "university" type that:

- a) Exercise academic and research-scientific activities continuously for at least ten years;
- b) Are accredited institutions;

c) Have employed at least eighteen members of academic staff holding the title "Professor," full-time, on contracts with unspecified durations. In any case, the university must have at least five full-time lecturers holding the title of professor in each faculty;

d) Offer doctoral studies or long-term specializations;

e) Fulfill additional criteria specified by the decision of the Council of Ministers

Ranking of Researchers

Albanian National H-index Ranking is an independent international ranking aimed at assessing the scientific productivity of scientists, research groups, and organizations in Albania based on the consolidated Hirsch index [30]. The Hirsch index is a unified scientific productivity metric used to evaluate the performance of scientists, research groups, journals, organizations, and countries. It is calculated using two variables: the citation index and the number of publications.

The ranking considers the total Hirsch index of Albania's scientific institutions, addressing information from scient metric databases and platforms such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. Based on these data, the National H-index Ranking indicator and the corresponding ranked position in the ranking (Position) are formed.

Brain drainage

Albania has seen a positive increase in higher education levels in the last decade as the share of university graduates aged 30-34 rose from 11.4% to 33.2% during 2012-2022, while this share reached 40.3% for the age group 25-29 during the same period (2012-2022). However, 27.5% of these graduates are unemployed[31]. 23 Albanian entities have endorsed the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the recruitment of researchers; only the University of Tirana was granted the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R) in 2020.

Albania is the country in the Western Balkans with the highest percentage of family members living abroad (32%). Emigration of the countries of South-East Europe is determined to a large extent by common “push factors such as troubled economies, political instability, severe unemployment, and lack of respect for human rights, including the right to work. Migration of highly skilled workers has accompanied Albania during the transition period and it still goes on. After the fall of the communist regime, the country faced a massive migration wave of the population to Western Europe countries, but also to the United States, Canada, and other developed countries. From a point of view of duration, degree, and impact on the development of the country, **Albania constitutes the most striking example of brain drain in South East Europe.** Indeed, Albania has one of the highest emigration rates in the world: during the 1990s almost 40% of lecturers and researchers left the country. Among these, 66% hold a PhD title. There are many examples of experts and students who study in Italy, Greece, Canada, and Germany, and it is estimated that only 5% of them will return.

Each year, around 2000 students leave the country to study abroad

[31] Albanian's ERA integration. 2023. An update by Policy Answers. https://wbc-rti.info/object/document/24663/attach/20231117_ERA_ALB.pdf

Workplace of academia, employment

Academic freedom

to the Law on Higher Education, Higher Education Institutions have academic freedom, and financial, organizational, and staff selection autonomy, following the law in force.

is guaranteed through the right:

- a. to organize teaching, research, innovation, and creative activities;
- b. to design and develop study programs and to define the areas of scientific research activity;
- c. to organize the process of promoting academic staff.

Status of Academic Staff

The academic staff enjoys special status and treatment. The special status and treatment are proposed by the Minister responsible for education, and approved by the Council of Ministers.

Public institutions of higher education may contribute to the special financial treatment of academic staff, in addition to benefits from the State Budget. Aspects of special treatment, as well as other benefits for academic staff of higher education institutions, are determined by the Administration Board. The rights and obligations of the staff of higher education institutions are determined by their statutes and internal regulations, in accordance with applicable laws and regulations.

Employment of Staff in Higher Education Institutions

The staff of higher education institutions consists of academic staff, assistant academic staff, and administrative staff. The staff of higher education institutions may be employed on contracts, for unspecified or specified periods, as well as on full-time or part-time engagements.

The rules and procedures for selecting members of the ad hoc commission, as well as the selection of academic staff, are specified in the statute of the higher education institution. Full-time academic staff in one higher education institution cannot be employed as full-time academic staff in another higher education institution, both within and outside the country.

Working hours dedicated to research and projects

Decision No. 29, 10.09.2018 of the Ministry of Education and Sports (MES) on the “Activity and Teaching Workload of the Academic Staff in Higher Education Institutions” [32] in Article 4 mentions that the time spent by the working groups writing projects for EU funds can be recognized as up to 350 teaching hours to be distributed among the team members. This allows for financial recognition of the time spent writing projects for each working group member. The 2023-2030 national strategy on employment and skills, adopted in 2023, prioritizes the systematic engagement of the private sector in vocational education and training, and the development of green and digital skills through a lifelong learning system that allows for effective upskilling and reskilling activities [33].

[32] Decision No. 29, 10.09.2018 of the Ministry of Education and Sports (MES) on the “Activity and Teaching Workload of the Academic Staff in Higher Education Institutions” <https://arsimi.gov.al/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/Udhezimi-nr.-29-dt-10.9.2018.pdf>

[33] Ministry of Finance and Economy. 2022. National Employment and Skills Strategy 2023–2030 https://arkiva.financa.gov.al/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/National-Employment-and-Skills-Strategy-2030_EN.pdf

Mental Health and Well-being in research and academia

Psychiatric treatments, psychotherapy, and psychosocial support are the main components of mental health therapies administered in Albania [33]. Many times, private practices, mental health facilities, and governmental hospitals offer these services. Other resources include helplines and nonprofit organizations that provide support and counseling [34]

Personal, social, and environmental problems such as unemployment, violence, and poverty pose a threat to mental health and overall well-being [34].

In the European Union, 125 million people, or 18% of the total population, suffered from mental health issues in 2019 [35]. Since 2010, the number of mental health issues recorded in Albania's primary healthcare clinics has been rising significantly, reaching over 40,000 cases by 2021[36]. The aging population and more mental health awareness are blamed for this trend. 2015 saw a dramatic rise in neurotic disorders, especially anxiety and depression, as a result of a new national program that introduced early identification [37].

According to a 2017 survey, 56% of women receiving Primary Health Care services had mental health issues [36]. A comparatively high rate of reported depression across age groups is shown earlier in research.

Albania, on the other hand, has the lowest rates of healthcare utilization for mental health in the European Region [38;39] with only 4,000 hospitalizations for mental illnesses annually. The most common problems impacted by the pandemic in 2020 were anxiety and addiction, with a low utilization rate [40].

About 3,500 people were admitted to hospitals in 2021, which was a little more than in 2020 but still less than in years prior [41]. Only a small percentage of common disorders, such as anxiety and depression, are treated by Primary Health Care in Albania; approximately 25% of cases involve schizophrenia [42].

34. European Parliament. Committee on Environment, Public Health and Food Safety. Rapporteur: Sara Cerdas. Report on mental health. 17.11.2023 - (2023/2074(INI)).
- A9-0367/2023. Available from: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-9-2023-0367_EN.html

35. World Health Organization. Comprehensive Mental Health Action Plan 2013–2030. Geneva; 2021. Available from: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/igo>.

36. Together for Life. Women and mental health in Albania: Public health policies and their gender approach towards mental health. We cannot advance health without advancing rights. (Project supported by the French Embassy in Tirana). 2023. Available from: <https://www.togetherforlife.org.al/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/Women-and-Mental-Health-in-Albania.pdf>

37. Gjonça A, Burazeri G, Ylli A, Subashi B, Hoxha R. Demographic and health challenges facing Albania in the 21st century. UNFPA; 2020. Available from: https://albania.unfpa.org/sites/default/files/pub-pdf/albania_demographic_health_challenges_report_2020_english_version.pdf.

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39. World Health Organization. Joint External Evaluation of IHR Core Capacities of Albania. Geneva; 2017. Available from: <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/254886/WHO-WHE-CPI-2017.18-eng.pdf?sequence=1>.

40. World Health Organization. Roadmap for Health and Well-being in the Western Balkans (2021–2025): Summary. European Program of Work (2020–2025) – "United Action for Better Health". Geneva; 2021. Available from: <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/345937/WHO-EURO-2021-3437-43196-60510-eng.pdf?sequence=1>.

41. Bucaj J, Mechili EA, Galanis P, Mersini B, Nika S, Hoxhaj I, Likaj S, Patelarou AE, Patelarou E. Decreased Hospital Visits and Increased Mortality Rate in Emergency Department during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Evidence from Albania. Acta Med Lit. 2022;29(1):58–68. doi: 10.15388/Amed.2022.29.1.13. Epub 2022 Jul 26. PMID: 36061927; PMCID: PMC9428650.

42. Doukani A, Cerga Pashoja A, Fanaj N, Qirjako G, Meksi A, Mustafa S, Vis C, Hug J. Organizational Readiness for Implementing an Internet-Based Cognitive Behavioral Therapy Intervention for Depression Across Community Mental Health Services in Albania and Kosovo: Directed Qualitative Content Analysis. JMIR Form Res. 2021 Nov 1;5(11):e29280. doi: 10.2196/29280. PMID: 34723822; PMCID: PMC8593793.

43. World Health Organization. WHO-AIMS report on mental health system in Albania: A report of the assessment of the mental health system in Albania using the World Health Organization – Assessment Instrument for Mental Health Systems (WHO-AIMS). Tirana, Albania; 2006. Available from: https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/mental-health/who-aims-country-reports/albania_who_aims_reportia.pdf?sfvrsn=1ee40476_3

44. Republic of Albania Ministry of Health. Action Plan For The Development Of Mental Health Services In Albania 2013–2022. 2013. Available from: https://shendetesia.gov.al/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/Plani_i_vperimit_per_Zhvillimin_e_Sherbimeve_te_Shendetit_Mendor_2013_-_2022.pdf

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The climate around mental health and well-being

obstacles to ask for mental health care

lack of knowledge about the provided services and their effectiveness

considerable budget and resource constraints

geographic differences, where access is better in urban than rural locations
[46;47]

A systematic strategy for mental health crisis intervention is lacking in many institutions

lack of qualified personnel and antiquated infrastructure

The government provides most mental health services in Albania, but there is not enough money to handle the country's rising need for them [48;49]. Many families may find it difficult to pay for mental health services out of pocket because there is a large percentage of the population for whom private insurance coverage is inadequate.

Specialist counseling or mental health assistance is not provided in the majority of facilities. Basic mental health support is provided by general healthcare facilities, although organizations sometimes lack qualified mental health experts [50]. Intervention quality and reach are further hampered by inadequate training for mental health providers, particularly in rural locations. Because there is often a waiting list for mental health services

46. Wainberg ML, Scorza P, Shultz JM, Helpman L, Mootz JJ, Johnson KA, Neria Y, Bradford JE, Oquendo MA, Arbuckle MR. Challenges and Opportunities in Global Mental Health: a Research-to-Practice Perspective. *Curr Psychiatry Rep.* 2017 May;19(5):28. doi: 10.1007/s11920-017-0780-z. PMID: 28425023; PMCID: PMC5553319.

47. World Health Organization. Mental Health Atlas 2020 Country Profile Albania. Geneva; 2022a. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/mental-health-atlas-alb-2020-country-profile>. Accessed May 2, 2024.

48. WHO Regional Office for Europe. Meeting to address mental health in the Western Balkans: Building back better from the COVID-19 pandemic and transforming mental health services: 24–25 October 2022, Tirana, Albania: Meeting report. Copenhagen; 2023. Available from: <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/372340/WHO-EURO-2023-7845-47613-70111-eng.pdf?sequence=1>.

49. World Health Organization. World mental health report: Transforming mental health for all. Geneva; 2022b. License: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO. Available from: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/igo>.

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Mental health support and service systems

The main stakeholder in Albania's mental health service system is the **Ministry of Health and Social Protection** which governs Albania's healthcare and social assistance services as well as finances all public mental health services, except school-based psychological counseling [51;52]. The Ministry of Health and Social Protection is the State Social Service.

Except for university hospitals, all levels of the health system's operational management and coordination of healthcare activities are under the purview of the **Central Directorate of the Health Care Service Operator** which comprises four regional directorates that oversee 36 Local Health Care Units and around 40 hospitals (both regional and municipal) [52]. Community-based Mental Health Centers and Supported Homes fall within the purview of Regional Directorates of Health and Social Care Organizations

A prominent player in creating a workforce for mental health services and spearheading attempts to put clinical practice guidelines into effect is the **University of Medicine, Tirana**. The University of Tirana's Faculty of Social Sciences, Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, and the recently established Orders of Psychologist and Social Worker are significant players in the development of human resources for mental health treatment. Social workers and psychologists are just now beginning the certification procedure.

Institutional accreditation of healthcare providers and professionals falls under the purview of the **Agency for Quality Assurance of Health and Social Services**, which was established in 2022 on the foundation of two previous agencies.

The **National Committee of Mental Health** is an advisory council guiding mental health legislation and policy. A recent report [53], with assistance from the WHO office in Albania, and the perspectives of several important informants states that the National Committee of Mental Health needs to be reorganized with the addition of additional organizations like the Ministry of Education, the University of Medicine, the Institute of Public Health, the Operator of Health Care, local governments, etc [54].

In Albania, **local governments** play a significant role in providing social protection and care. Some vulnerable populations with mental health concerns are among their beneficiaries. Through its administrative units spread throughout the territory, Local government manages the family aid application procedure. The units of evaluation of needs and referral of cases will serve as the hubs for case management. The Law of Social Care states that each Local government should have one psychiatrist for every 10,000 residents.

51. Council of Ministers. Decision No. 405, dated 20.5.2020 on the approval of the primary healthcare development strategy in Albania 2020-2025. 2020 [cited 2024 Jun 11]. Available from: <https://shendetesia.gov.al/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/Strategjia-Zhvillimit-t%C3%AB-Kujdesi-Paresor-2020-2025.pdf>

52. Ministry of Health and Social Protection & World Health Organization, Regional Office for Europe. (2021). National Health Strategy 2023-2030. Retrieved April 11, 2024, from https://extranet.who.int/countryplanningcycles/sites/default/files/public_file_rep/ALB_Albania_RENJK-National-Health-Strategy_2021-2030.pdf

53. World Health Organization b. South-eastern Europe Health Network. 2023. Available from: [https://www.who.int/europe/groups/south-eastern-europe-health-network-\(seehn\)](https://www.who.int/europe/groups/south-eastern-europe-health-network-(seehn)).

54. Westminster Foundation for Democracy Limited (WFD). Advocacy in Health Care in Albania: Actors, Achievements and Challenges. Assessment Report. September 2022. Available from: https://www.wfd.org/sites/default/files/2022-10/Advocacy%20in%20health%20care_ENG_FINAL.pdf.

Mental health support and service systems

Conventions at the international level

Albania, a member of the United Nations, follows rules for protecting those with mental health. Abuse of individuals with mental illnesses may violate their human rights, according to international law [55]. Albania has accepted the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and has been a member of the Council of Europe since 1995 [56]. Albania has severe deficiencies in the rule of law, notwithstanding improved national legislation and international accords. Albania ranked 87th out of 140 nations in 2022. Albania ratified the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) by Law no. 1769 [57]. The country has ratified both the Convention against Torture and the Convention for Civil and Political Rights [58].

55. Commission Staff Working Document. Albania 2022 Report. Brussels; 12 October 2022. Accompanying the document Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions 2022 Communication on EU Enlargement policy. Available from: <https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-10/Albania%20Report%202022.pdf>

56. Council of Europe. Albania // 46 States, one Europe. Action of the Council of Europe in Albania. Available from: <https://www.coe.int/en/web/portal/albania>

57. Council of Europe. Report on the implementation of recommendations addressed to Albania by the Committee of the Parties of Council of Europe Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence (Istanbul Convention). Available from: <https://rm.coe.int/albania-report-on-the-implementation-of-the-recommendations-from-cp-ic/1680a30d7f>.

58. United Nations. Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment. Available from: <https://docstore.ohchr.org/SelfServices/FilesHandler.ashx?enc=6QkG1d%2FPPrICAqhKb7yhsjThpCuiQQq%2Bi%2B6mI3upUdInbSySbIQpNIT27k gSwwp0XH2h4LiuRvb0GV%2BlbjFKYR%2FDpIdoTcjGft5vZ0pQw8I5%2FhZxaYilricbEyzECw>.

The Ministry of Health and Social Protection is in charge of overseeing Albania's healthcare and social assistance systems.

The integration of these systems at the central level provides an excellent chance to solve complicated challenges related to mental health issues.

The National Mental Health Committee is an essential policy coordinating organization that is responsible for overseeing the execution of the country's mental health legal framework.

The Ministry of Health and Social Protection has launched the Albanian National Health Strategy 2023–2030 [52], to ensure equal access to mental health services for all. It is the Ministry of Health and Social Protection's most important strategic document and an overarching platform for coordinating all efforts to improve the health and well-being of all Albanians. The strategy's goal is to continue efforts to promote the health and well-being of the Albanian people while respecting their right to good health between 2023 and 2030. The strategy recommends integrating mental health services into primary health care and collaborating with current providers like NGOs to improve local and national responses to mental health concerns in Albania. Investing in mental health services, particularly for youth, and building local capacity to treat mental health issues through primary health care should be prioritized. There is no mention of researchers or academic staff in the strategy.

Albania's main mental health policy document is the National Action Plan for Mental Health 2023–2026 [59]. The action plan outlines the integrated mental health services outlined in Article 10, Chapter 2 of the Mental Health Law [60]. These services include primary health care, community mental health services, ambulatory specialist services, and specialized mental health services [52]. The first three categories of services can be delivered by both publicly and privately sponsored organizations/initiatives. Over the past two decades, mental health services have shifted from hospitals to community and family care, with a focus on decentralization and interdisciplinary teams. The National Plan's principle of 'equity' in accessing services applies to diverse socio-economic categories. There is no mention of researchers or academic staff in the strategy.

59. Ministry of Health and Social Protection. (2023). Mental Health Action Plan Albania 2023–2026. Retrieved May 2, 2024, from <https://shendetesia.gov.al/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/Plani-i-Veprimit-per-Shendetin-Mendor-2023-2026.pdf>.

60. Law No. 44/2012 "On Mental Health". Available from: https://shendetesia.gov.al/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/Ligji_Nr.44_2012_per_shendetin_mendor.pdf.